

CERTAIN ASPECTS OF REFORMING THE PROSECUTION AUTHORITIES OF UKRAINE**Kucheryavyi P.**postgraduate student of the National Academy Bohdan Khmelnytskyi
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14984000>**Abstract**

This article is devoted to the issue of the prosecution bodies of Ukraine. The article provides a thorough analysis of the prosecution system, identifies the peculiarities of creation and liquidation of prosecution bodies. The changes in the structure of the prosecutor's office caused by the reforms aimed at ensuring the rule of law, increasing the efficiency of work and strengthening the responsibility of prosecutors are considered. The author identifies the key challenges faced by the prosecutor's office in its activities, in particular in the context of law enforcement reform, adaptation to European standards and the fight against corruption. It is established that in 2019 there were changes in the prosecution system and military prosecutor's offices were liquidated. The liquidation of military prosecutor's offices in Ukraine is an issue that requires in-depth analysis in terms of expediency, legal consequences and impact on the military justice system. On the one hand, the reform of the prosecutor's office was aimed at optimizing its structure, reducing excessive centralization and bringing it in line with European standards. However, on the other hand, the destruction of a specialized body that supervised the observance of the rule of law in the military sphere has created significant risks for ensuring an adequate level of military justice, especially in the context of the ongoing armed aggression against Ukraine. The author analyzes the experience of the Republic of Poland in organizing the activities of the prosecutor's office. It is found that the realities of time require the return of military prosecutors to the system of these bodies. The author provides recommendations for improving the legislation in terms of regulating the activities of prosecutors. The restoration of the military prosecutor's office in Ukraine should be based on the following key principles: a clear definition of competence, independence in decision-making, and consistency with international standards of military justice. The introduction of such an institution will increase the effectiveness of war crimes investigations, ensure control over the observance of the rights of servicemen and contribute to the strengthening of the rule of law in the military sphere. In this regard, we believe that the establishment of military prosecutor's offices should be enshrined in law by amending Article 7 of the Law of Ukraine "On the Prosecutor's Office" and including military prosecutor's offices in the system of prosecutorial bodies.

Keywords: prosecutor's office, reforms, military justice, military prosecutor's office, specialized prosecutor's office.

Introduction. The realities of the time indicate that the sphere of functioning of the prosecutor's office is under the influence of a number of problems arising from various circumstances. Constant changes in the national legislation regulating the activities of the prosecutor's office cause an objective deterioration in the quality of lawmaking and contribute to situations of legislative conflicts. Another difficulty is the unofficial involvement of the prosecutor's office in the political field of the state, which violates the principles of prosecutorial neutrality established by law. The prosecutor's office should remain independent and impartial, ensuring protection of the interests of the state and society without being influenced by political views or decisions of individual officials [1, pp. 7-15]. The issue of the status of the prosecutor's office was studied by N.P. Osipov, V.D. Vodnik, G.P. Klimov, N.P. Osipova, Y.P. Surmin, V.D. Bakumenko, A.M. Mikhnenko, Y.V. Kovbasyuk, V.P. Troshchynskyi, L.V. Borodych, S.P. Kondrakov, Y. Hroshevyi, V. Dolezian, V. Zelenetskyi, P. Karkach, M. Kosiuta, A. Linnik, O. Mykhailenko, M. Mychko, M. Rudenko, V. Sukhonos, V. Tatsiy, S. Banakh, and many others. At the same time, some issues still remain unresearched due to the dynamism of legislation, geopolitical changes, and a full-scale war and require study and analysis. Summary of the main material. Reforming the prosecution service also faces

challenges, as this process can change its priorities depending on the political landscape and external factors. Even with the intensification of measures to improve the administrative and legal support of the prosecution service and the legal framework, there are problems in this area. In particular, at the national level, there is uncertainty about the concept of administrative and legal support of the prosecutor's office and the methods of its activities, and the lack of a clear definition of the branch of government to which this body belongs, unlike in the European experience. Additionally, there is a problem with the use of contradictory categorical and conceptual apparatus in regulations, and the issue of administrative and legal principles of the prosecutor's activity in Ukraine has not been studied in legal doctrine.

Reforming the prosecution system in Ukraine is an important area of improvement for the justice system, due to both internal challenges and the need to harmonize with European standards. In particular, against the backdrop of the ongoing armed aggression against Ukraine, the issue of establishing a military prosecutor's office that would differ from specialized prosecutors in the defense sector is of particular relevance. In this context, we should support the point of view of Ukrainian researcher O. Kozachuk that changes in the system of prosecution bodies of Ukraine should be car-

ried out in a balanced manner, based on a comprehensive, systematic approach and scientific substantiation [2, P. 22].

The current state of organization of the prosecutor's office in Ukraine is determined by the Law of Ukraine "On the Prosecutor's Office" and a number of bylaws regulating the activities of this institution. Thus, according to the mentioned law, the prosecution system of Ukraine consists of: The Office of the Prosecutor General; regional prosecutor's offices; district prosecutor's offices; and the Specialized Anti-Corruption Prosecutor's Office [3]. At the same time, the Annex to the Law of Ukraine "On the Prosecutor's Office" provided for the list and territorial jurisdiction of local and military prosecutors, i.e. the existence and activities of military prosecutors. In August 2019, President of Ukraine V. Zelenskyy submitted as an urgent draft law No. 1032 aimed at reforming the prosecution authorities, including the liquidation of the military prosecutor's office. It is important to note that this draft law was put into practice by the adoption of the Law of Ukraine "On Amendments to Certain Legislative Acts of Ukraine on Priority Measures for the Reform of the Prosecution Service" of September 19, 2019, No. 113-IX, which demonstrated the existence of the relevant political will to implement the reform, according to paragraph 24 of which, the Annex "List and Territorial Jurisdiction of Local and Military Prosecutor's Offices" to the Law of Ukraine "On the Prosecution Service" shall cease to be effective from the date of commencement of the work of district prosecutor's offices [4]. Thus, military prosecutor's offices in Ukraine were liquidated. Instead, the Order of the Prosecutor General's Office "On Certain Issues of Ensuring the Functioning of Specialized Defense Prosecutor's Offices (as District Prosecutor's Offices)" of 17.03.2023 No. 75, in particular its Annex, provides for a list of specialized defense prosecutor's offices (as district prosecutor's offices).

As V. Vdovychenko correctly noted, the liquidation of military prosecutor's offices may negatively affect the system of training specialists with specialized knowledge in the field of military legislation and the specifics of military service. The disappearance of such a structure could lead to a shortage of personnel familiar with the nuances of using military property, subordination in military units, the peculiarities of military equipment, strategy and tactics of warfare. This, in turn, can lead to a decrease in the level of pre-trial investigation in cases related to the military sphere, as well as weaken the protection of the rights of servicemen and state interests in the field of defense [5]. In our opinion, in practice, this situation has arisen. The liquidation of military prosecutor's offices in Ukraine is an issue that requires in-depth analysis from the point of view of expediency, legal consequences and impact on the military justice system. On the one hand, the reform of the prosecutor's office was aimed at optimizing its structure, reducing excessive centralization and bringing it in line with European standards. However, on the other hand, the destruction of a specialized body that supervised the observance of the rule of law in the military sphere created significant risks for ensuring an adequate level of military justice, especially in the context

of the ongoing armed aggression against Ukraine. The military prosecutor's office performed important functions, including procedural guidance in criminal proceedings for war crimes, monitoring the observance of the rule of law in military formations, and investigating crimes related to treason, desertion, and abuse of power in the military. The specifics of these crimes require not only a deep knowledge of general criminal and administrative law, but also an understanding of the military structure, subordination, combat tactics, and the specifics of storage and use of military property. The elimination of the military prosecutor's office has called into question the effectiveness of investigating such offenses, as general prosecutors and investigators who do not have the appropriate military training may face difficulties in law enforcement. One of the arguments in favor of abolishing military prosecutor's offices was that their functions could be performed by specialized units within the general structure of the prosecution service. However, in practice, this approach does not solve the problem of lack of personnel with relevant knowledge and experience. The formation of new specialized prosecutor's offices requires a long time and additional resources, which is a critical drawback in the context of martial law. Thus, assessing the feasibility of liquidating military prosecutor's offices, it can be argued that this decision was premature and insufficiently justified, especially given the security challenges faced by Ukraine. In the context of the armed conflict and the need for enhanced control over the observance of the rule of law in the military sphere, it would be more appropriate not to liquidate this institution but to reform it, improving its mechanisms of functioning, raising the level of training and adapting its activities to modern challenges.

With the outbreak of full-scale war, there was a need to restore a specialized body that would provide procedural guidance in the investigation of war crimes and ensure an appropriate level of military justice.

The establishment of a military prosecutor's office should be justified by the complex needs of the defense sector and state security. The difference between the military prosecutor's office and specialized defense prosecutors is the broader competence of the former. While specialized defense prosecutor's offices deal mainly with economic crimes and corruption in the defense sector, the military prosecutor's office should be aimed at investigating war crimes, violations of international humanitarian law, and ensuring the proper functioning of military justice.

The European experience confirms the expediency of military prosecutors' offices in countries with strong defense structures or involved in armed conflicts. For example, let's try to analyze the system of prosecutors in Poland.

The current Law on the Public Prosecutor's Office was adopted by the Parliament of the Republic of Poland on January 28, 2016 [6]. This legal act comprehensively defines the principles of activity and functioning of the prosecution authorities. It replaced the previous legislation that had been in force since 1985, but no longer met the modern needs of Poland as a state gov-

erned by the rule of law, as well as the challenges associated with the development of criminal schemes, including terrorism, organized crime, financial and economic offenses. According to this law, the Prosecutor General (Prokurator Generalny) is the highest prosecutorial authority. The position of the Prosecutor General is held by the Minister of Justice. The prosecutors of the general organizational units of the prosecutor's office are the prosecutors of the National Prosecutor's Office, regional prosecutor's offices, district prosecutor's offices and district prosecutor's offices. Prosecutors of the Institute of National Remembrance are prosecutors of the Main Commission for Investigation of Crimes against the Polish People, prosecutors of regional commissions for investigation of crimes against the Polish people, prosecutors of the Lustration Bureau and prosecutors of regional lustration bureaus [6]. The organization of the prosecution in Poland, as defined by the 2016 Act on the Prosecution Service, seems to be well-structured and effective. The Prosecutor General, who is also the Minister of Justice, has a central role in the system, which allows for a unified national prosecution policy. This centralization in leadership is important for maintaining unity in the prosecution service and implementing a common strategy at the national level. At the same time, a decentralized structure, including regional and district prosecutor's offices, allows for more flexibility in adapting the work of the prosecution service to specific local conditions, which increases the effectiveness and timeliness of the response to crime. The existence of specialized units, such as those dealing with crimes against national memory through the Institute of National Memory, is an important step in ensuring truth and justice for society, especially in matters relating to historical crimes. These specialized prosecutor's offices allow for a deeper understanding of the specifics of such crimes and high-level investigations. In addition, the system of prosecutor's offices ensures close supervision and control at various stages of the criminal process, which reduces the risks of corruption and increases the efficiency of judicial investigations. Therefore, the Polish model of prosecution organization seems to be suitable for law enforcement, with an emphasis on specialization and justice in important areas, such as historical memory and local issues that can have a significant impact on society. According to the Polish Law on Prosecution of 2016, the military prosecutor's office is not a separate body, and military oversight and investigation functions are carried out through a specialized department within the National Prosecutor's Office. This department is responsible for ensuring the rule of law in the army and investigating war crimes. Military prosecutors exercise legal oversight over the activities of the military forces and investigate offenses related to military service. Military prosecutors carry out their tasks through the military affairs department of the National Prosecutor's Office, as well as in district and regional prosecutor's offices dealing with military matters. They have the right to exercise their functions in cases that are not subject to the jurisdiction of military courts. Prosecutors who are military officers may

perform their duties during mobilization, the introduction of martial law or in case of war, and may also be called up for military service [6].

This analysis of the Polish law "On the Public Prosecutor's Office" allowed us to conclude that the existence of a body dealing with military issues in the system of prosecutors is extremely appropriate and necessary. In particular, it becomes so in relation to the Ukrainian realities when the war is ongoing, when military justice is aimed at ensuring the rule of law in the military sphere. In addition, draft law 6569-d, which was voted in June 2024 and is a revised version of draft laws 6569 and 6569-1, aims to create a military police. The adoption of the draft law is justified by the fact that the current Military Police does not currently have any powers to carry out operational and investigative measures and bring perpetrators to legal responsibility, and is limited in its ability to assist pre-trial investigation bodies and prosecutors. In addition, it is necessary to "fill in" the existing gaps in the legislation, which, against the background of the specific structure of the Armed Forces and other military formations in Ukraine, indicate the need for a coherent system of military justice in the country. Among the arguments of the draft law are the inefficiency and ineffectiveness of the investigation of numerous military offenses and the fact that SBI investigators do not fully ensure the fulfillment of their tasks due to limited powers and imperfect legislation. In addition, the workload of the SBI has increased significantly since 2022. For example, 85.5% of registered criminal proceedings against military personnel in 2023 concerned violations of the rules of service, which obviously affects the quality and speed of crime solving. The draft law proposes to create a new military formation with law enforcement functions - the Military Police. Its task is to ensure law and order and military discipline in the Ministry of Defense of Ukraine, the Armed Forces of Ukraine and the State Special Transport Service. One of the significant changes envisaged by the draft law is that the Military Police will be empowered to carry out operational and investigative activities, and in some cases even to conduct investigative (search) and covert investigative (search) actions. Previously, the HCJ only assisted special agencies in carrying out such activities. The newly created body will be financed by redistributing expenses in the state budget and expenses for those bodies whose functions will be taken over by the Military Police. According to the text of the document, the work of the Military Police will be coordinated by the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine through the Minister of Defense, and during martial law, the overall management and coordination will be carried out by the Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces. The Military Police is to be formed from active servicemen of the Armed Forces of Ukraine. According to the draft law, the total number of its members may not exceed 1.5% of the total number of the Armed Forces [7].

Given all of the above, and in light of the possible creation of a military police, we believe that it is time to return to Ukraine military prosecutor's offices, whose prosecutors will provide procedural guidance in pre-

trial investigations and supervise compliance with legislation in the military sphere, which, as already emphasized, requires prosecutors with special knowledge and skills.

The restoration of the military prosecutor's office in Ukraine should be based on the following key principles: clear definition of competence, independence in decision-making, and consistency with international standards of military justice. The introduction of such an institution will increase the effectiveness of war crimes investigations, ensure control over the observance of the rights of servicemen and contribute to the strengthening of the rule of law in the military sphere. In this regard, we believe that the establishment of military prosecutor's offices should be enshrined in law by amending Article 7 of the Law of Ukraine "On Prosecution" and including military prosecutor's offices in the system of prosecution bodies, since part 2 of Article 7 of the Law of Ukraine "On Prosecution" in terms of granting the Prosecutor General the right to establish specialized prosecutor's offices as a structural unit of the Office of the Prosecutor General, regional prosecutor's offices, district prosecutor's offices, if necessary, does not fully align with Paragraph 14 of Article 92 of the Constitution of Ukraine.

Thus, the creation of a military prosecutor's office is a relevant and reasonable step in the context of reforming the law enforcement system of Ukraine. This is also emphasized by O.V. Shamara, who proposes to create (restore) the Specialized Military Prosecutor's Office. The introduction of the Specialized Military Prosecutor's Office, consisting of military personnel, during martial law will allow to effectively protect national interests from threats, ensure law and order in the military sphere and supervise the activities of intelligence and counterintelligence agencies. In addition, this body aims to improve the effectiveness of investigating war crimes and crimes against humanity, as well as the implementation of counterintelligence measures [8, pp. 241-250]. To this end, a draft law "On the Organizational and Legal Framework for the Construction and Functioning of the Military Justice of Ukraine" has already been proposed to the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine and registered, which will facilitate the creation of a military justice system in wartime. According to this draft law, the system of state bodies that are part of the Military Justice of Ukraine includes: 1. military police. 2. Military counterintelligence and pre-trial investigation body of a special purpose state body with law enforcement functions that ensures the state security of Ukraine. 3. The military prosecutor's office. 4. Military advocacy. 5. Military court. Article 7 of the above-mentioned draft law contains the specifics of the military prosecutor's office, in particular, the Specialized Military Prosecutor's Office in Ukraine is headed by the Chief Military Prosecutor, who is a Deputy Prosecutor General. The prosecutors of this prosecutor's office are military officers, and their service procedure is determined by regulatory legal acts. Military prosecu-

tor's offices are staffed by officers serving under contract or mobilized persons who are seconded to perform the duties defined by the Law of Ukraine "On the Prosecutor's Office" [9]. However, in September 2024, this draft law was withdrawn from consideration by the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine. We strongly believe that the adoption of such a draft law is extremely relevant given the current situation in the country.

Conclusions. The conditions of martial law and the constant threat of external aggression require an effective and systematic organization of military justice. Such a law will optimize the system of law enforcement agencies in the military sphere, ensure uniform legal practice and help improve coordination of actions in ensuring national security. At the same time, taking into account European experience and adapting to the conditions of martial law and the post-war period will help to increase the efficiency of the prosecutor's office and ensure an appropriate level of law and order in the defense sector.

References:

1. Malyarenko V.T. The word of the judge about the prosecutor and the prosecutor's office. Bulletin of the National Academy of Prosecution of Ukraine. 2008. № 2. P. 7-15.
2. Kozachuk O.S. Organizational and Legal Principles of Functioning of Military Prosecutor's Offices in Ukraine: Candidate of Law (PhD): 12.00.10. Kyiv, 2016. 228 p.
3. Law of Ukraine "On the Prosecutor's Office" of 14.10.2014 No. 1697-VII. Bulletin of the Verkhovna Rada (VVR), 2015, No. 2-3, p. 12.
4. On Amendments to Certain Legislative Acts of Ukraine on Priority Measures for the Reform of the Public Prosecution Service: Law of Ukraine of 19.09.2019 No. 113-IX. URL: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/113-20>.
5. Vitalii Vdovitchenko. Foreign models of bodies of the military prosecutor's office functioning. Visegrad Journal on Human Rights. URL: <https://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://journals.indexcopernicus.com/api/file/viewByFileId/907835>.
6. Ustawa z dnia 28 stycznia 2016 r. "Prawo o prokuraturze": tekst ujednolicony. Dziennik Ustaw Rzeczypospolitej Polskiej. 2016. Poz. 177. URL: <http://prawo.sejm.gov.pl/isap.nsf/download.xsp/WDU20160000177/U/D20160177Lj.pdf>.
7. What the future law on military police will change. URL: <https://parlament.org.ua/analytics/shho-zminyt-majbutnij-zakon-pro-vijskovu-policziyu/>.
8. Shamara O.V. Restoration of the military prosecutor's office as an element of the system of military justice of Ukraine. Information and law. № 1(48)/2024. C. 241-250.
9. Draft Law on the Organizational and Legal Framework for the Construction and Functioning of the Military Justice of Ukraine. URL: <https://itd.rada.gov.ua/billInfo/Bills/Card/42777>.